

TEENAGE MOTHERS AND PREGNANCY RELATED CHALLENGES IN TRADITIONAL SOCIETIES OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The rise in teenage pregnancy seems to be on the rise after there was break in the rate for sometimes in Akwa Ibom State due to the influence of the Free and Compulsory Education programme of the Akwa Ibom State government. This has called for concern which motivated the researchers to embark on examining the pregnancy related challenges, among adolescent mothers in traditional societies of Akwa Ibom State. Secondary data were analysed on itemized perceived challenges of teenage mothers in some communities in Akwa Ibom State. Literature was reviewed accordingly and conclusion was drawn that among teenager who are pregnant in Akwa Ibom State, challenges during pregnancy are frequent, however, several and severe complications may occur if those challenges are left undetected and untreated. Apart from the pregnancy related infections among adolescent mothers, they also experience many physical, psychological, mental and socio-economics challenges. It was recommended that there is need for school and community awareness to reduce the rampant case of unwanted and teenage pregnancy becomes eminent especially in traditional societies. Community leaders should as well be involved in the fight against barbaric cultures/practices that will expose girl's child to early marriages and its anticipants, through cultural reorientation programmes.

KEYWORDS: Teenage Mother, Pregnancy, Challenges and Traditional Societies

INTRODUCTION

Motherhood is significantly an important event in the life of a woman and for most women, it has been associated with several health and other problems. To Manegli, Rayyani, Cheraglic and Tirgari (2017), the problems could be traced to the state of pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum and breast feeding. Statistics (WHO, 2019) showed that about 810 women died from preventable causes related to pregnancy and childbirth a year. The sub-Saharan Africa

and Southern Asia accounted for 86 percent (254,000) of the established global maternal deaths in 2017; and the sub-Saharan Africa alone accounted for roughly two-thirds (196,000) of maternal deaths (WHO, 2019).

Pregnancy related challenges among adolescent mothers are commons in traditional societies. It however ranges from infectious diseases, poverty, forced and early marriages, peer influence, illiteracy and believe system as well as poor cultural practices.

Diseases as part of the related challenges experience by teenage mothers. They (disease) are disorders caused by pathogenic microorganisms (which could be either through bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites etc) and may be transmitted directly or indirectly by various sources (e.g., person to person, insects, animals, environment, food, water). Diseases are either preventable or treatable, all depending on how it may be managed by the victim. Certain patient's populations may also be more susceptible to infections, especially the Adolescent mothers in the interior societies/ setting and their perception of infection is a factor that depends on the nature of their community. During pregnancy, some common infections like vaginal yeast infections, group B streptococcus, bacterial vaginosis, and listeria, may occur which affects the processes of child bearing.

Studies (Ben and Daniel, 2023) shows that changes in immune function may cause the increased risk of infection, and if left untreated, may lead to serious complications which may range from severe infections during pregnancy that may lead it preterm birth, low birth weight, birth defects, learning problems, and possibly pregnancy loss. Prevention, early detection, and treatment are vital to help minimize and eliminate these complications with multiple available prevention and treatment strategies.

Moreover, changes in immune function, such as reduction in T- and B-cell activity and natural killer-cell activity and increases in dendritic-cell activity, may cause this increased risk of infection among adolescent mothers. The severity of some infections, such as; GBS, sexually transmitted disease and urinary tract infections, may also increase with advancing pregnancy stage (Smith, 2009). The study seeks to identify through secondary data the pregnancy related challenges, among adolescent mothers in traditional societies of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

WHO (2017), submits that pregnancy period is characterized by various challenges. According to Ben, Daniel and Peters (2023), there are challenges always associated with factors such as social, economic, cultural, demographic and environmental. To the authors, (Ben, Daniel and Peters, 2023), a catalogue of some of these related challenges that affects women while in pregnancy bothered on the economic status of their family, believe system, location of hospital.

In a studies by Ben and Daniel (2023) on disease prevalence and infant mortality in the rural areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, the authors submit that the spurt of disease lies on varied conditions including in equality of conditions of the environment in which the people live. This could be associated with usage drinking water, poor and costly healthcare services, poor sanitation, poor housing conditions and malnutrition among other. Nigeria's maternal

mortality rate is still as high as 917 deaths per 100,000,000 live births whereas for every 1,000 births, Akwa Ibom records 42 infants' deaths and maternal mortality in the state ranks among the worst in the country with 279 deaths per 100,000 births.

It is pertinent to note that maternal role attainment is a process that requires necessary abilities, which demands appropriate attitude as well as proper maternal identity. However, statistics shows that many women may still be at cross road of maternal death if the challenges characterizing the pregnancy are not identified and solved. Families particularly those of low income background and poor level of education, teenage motherhood, barbaric religious and cultural practices are the most affected despite advances in health technology and global awareness of modern methods of preventing and protecting pregnancy related challenges.

Adolescent Mothers and Problems Associated with Pregnancy

Adolescent mothers are birth female who are between the ages of 11 and 19 who become pregnant delivered and as well parent their children. They are otherwise called teenage mothers. Accepting the role of motherhood is associated with emotional and mental stress such as fear and worry, regret and frustration, guilt and shame, depression, and disruption in relationship of parties involved. Fear and worry according to Vicent and Alemu (2016) was mainly derived from incompetence to accept the responsibilities of motherhood. According to the authors, teenage mothers were also worried about difficult situations in pregnancy and childbirth which were caused by insufficient physical maturity and the regret associated with unwanted pregnancy, demands associated with or related to pregnancy and motherhood, as well as loss of previous desired position. Importantly also is incompetence in performing the maternal role which developed a sense of guilt and self-blame WHO (2019) noted that some teenage mothers experienced depression, particularly in the postpartum period. They are faced with series of challenges, and according to Ben, Daniel and Peters (2023) a number of issues led to a state of confusion and anxiety among pregnant women during the crisis period.

Vincent and Alemu (2016) noted that emotional and physical changes of teenage mothers led to tension and disruption of relationship with partners and family. According to the authors emotional and mental distress was another problem faced by teenage mothers, as they had experienced fear, worry, regret, frustration, guilt, shame, depression, and disruption in relationships. Teenage mothers experience fear of inability to accept the maternal responsibilities, shock, depression, denial, fear, shame, regret, loneliness, social isolation, and mental exhaustion. Adaptation to mothering and adolescence, dependence on others, unwanted pregnancy, poor decision making and problem solving, severe fatigue, unpreparedness, lack of time and energy, repetitive tasks, lack of social support, stigma, and taking responsibility alone are sources of stress for teenage mothers as well as multiple mental Stress have all been indentified to have affected the performance and health of the mother and her family adversely.

RESULT

CHALLENGES OF TEENAGE MOTHER PREGNANCY

Reasons for Adolescent Pregnancy

The factors contributing to teenage pregnancy are multifactorial, ranging from individual-behaviour, traditional and socio-cultural to religious in nature. Inarguably, low socio-economic status, limited education and early sexual activity can perpetuate a lot of challenges during teenage pregnancy. Vincent and Alemu (2016) identified some Factors contributing to as effects of teenage pregnancy to include:

- Lack of information about sexual and reproductive health and rights.
- Inadequate access to services tailored to young people by government NGOs and other multinational organisations.
- Family, community and social pressure to marry and the problem of adaption to the responsibilities of early motherhood.
- Sexual violence, economic demands on child rearing.
- Lack of education and/or becoming school drop-out.

Child, Early and Forced Marriage

This is one of the main contributors to teenage pregnancy in traditional societies is forced marriage. Measures to delay age at marriage can help reduce early pregnancies. The believes by parents that early marriage would safe their daughters from sexual abuse thus reducing the problem of infertility and recovery shame of unwanted pregnancy from the family causes other pregnancy related challenges in the life of the young girl.

Poverty

The level of poverty in some families in Akwa Ibom State has pushes and causes the rampant teenage pregnancy we see today in the society. This is because the parents are unable to cater for the needs of their wards, thereby leading to school dropout and exposing the female children to street hawking, which is dangerous and the effects could be early pregnancy infection and dead. Social determinants of health, such as low education and low income levels of a teen's family, may contribute to high teen birth rates. Teens in certain communities are at higher risk of teen pregnancy, HIV Infection and other related diseases and dead than young people traditional societies.

Youthful/Teenage Exuberance

According to Collins Dictionary, Exuberance is behaviour which is anxious, energetic, excited, and cheerful. It could also mean high spirits, energy, enthusiasm and vitality in their approach to things.

Contextually, youthful/teenage exuberance is the “conscious” display of the cheerfulness in them not minding the dangers ahead. The young girl at this age always wants to tell the world that they have arrived, they don't listen to instructions/advice, and before they realize they have fallen victims of teenage pregnancy and other health challenges. This has

been a scenario report from some river areas of Akwa Ibom State (Peters and Bassey, 2020)

Peer Influence

Young girls in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State like in Ibeno are commonly and negatively influenced by their peers/friends. Their behaviour till towards that of their friends because they want to be like them and since negative influence is easy to come by, they copy their friend's negative lifestyle. It affects both the victim who may be influenced into crime and the society at large.

Illiteracy

The most serious setback in the most rural societies in Akwa Ibom State is the problem of poverty. This affects every aspect of the people's life including educations. When a young girl/child does not envisage the resultant effects of her actions, Who does not have hope/plans for a secure tomorrow, and does make education her priority, her behaviour could be dangerous later in future. One effect could be teenage pregnancy. Where the family cannot give the child education – which is the basic need of life, the child is left at the mercy of friends who now influence her into negative behaviour.

Effects/Consequences of Adolescent Pregnancy

In addition to higher rates of postpartum depression, adolescent mothers have higher rates of depression than married women. They also have higher rates of suicidal ideation than their peers who aren't mothers. Adolescent mothers are more likely to experience posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) than other teenage women, as well because of their unpreparedness to carry a child and societal expectations from them. This is experienced in Akwa Ibom State where parents and guardians have neglected their roles (Bassey and Peters, 2021).

Financial Problems

Due to stigma and shame, pregnant teenager are often forced to stop schooling and this reduces their chances to hold a decent job and have a good income which will limits their opportunities to build a better life in future. Poor income may have adverse consequences on the nutrition and care of the unborn baby. The mother will however faced financial challenges ranges from the cost demand of accessing medical services and the child's upkeep (Ben, Daniel and Peters, 2023).

Health Challenges

The most important of the consequences of teenage pregnancy is the health challenges or havoc that it will cause both to the mother and the baby. In some communities like Ikot Nkang, Oto Akan, in Akwa Ibom State, there is a high tendency that the teenager who gets pregnancy will be affected; one by her economic status which will made it difficult for her to pay for her needs and secondly by emotional factors which will affects her enablement to cope (Ben, Daniel and Peters, 2023). Others include; mental health and pregnancy induced hypertension.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Among teenager who are pregnant in Akwa Ibom State, challenges during pregnancy

are frequent, however, several and severe complications may occur if those challenges are left undetected and untreated. Monitoring for any sign and symptoms of infection during pregnancy is important, as well as following appropriate prevention and treatment strategies to help prevent the risk of complications in pregnancy and the newborn.

Apart from the pregnancy related infections among adolescent mothers, they also experience many physical, psychological, mental and social challenges. Therefore, it is expedient that special attention and care support be made available to them by health care providers. A comprehensive understanding of the challenges encountered by adolescent mothers, will aid the development of culturally appropriate and health promotion guidelines and strategies. Most teenage mothers needed to receive support to expose them to their new roles as mothers, increased responsibilities, health problems, rising costs, and knowledge deficit. Without which inadequate support may to cause them experience serious challenges in adapting to motherhood.

On the threat of economic legend illiteracy the study recommends the need for government and non-governmental organizations to organize an awareness campaign to sensitize families, and young people on the dangers victims may likely face and the need to guide against.

The need for school and community awareness to reduce the rampant case of unwanted and teenage pregnancy becomes eminent especially in traditional societies. Community leaders should as well be involved in the fight against barbaric cultures/practices that will expose girl's child to early marriages and its anticipants, through cultural reorientation programmes.

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